

DFT analysis for the regio- and stereospecific synthesis of antibacterial isoxazolidine

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Abstract : Cycloaddition reaction of *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitron to methyl vinyl ketone generates stereospecific isoxazolidine possessing antibacterial properties. In the present report, detailed theoretical study at DFT/B3LYP/6-311G+(d,p) level of theory has been carried out to analyze the preferred regio- and stereospecific mode of the reaction. Global properties of the reactants have been computed to predict the electron demand character of the reaction. The selectivities have been rationalised on the basis of the local properties, interaction energies and activation parameters of the located transition states along the reaction pathway. Two different approaches have been employed for the calculations of interaction energies. The theoretical predictions were in complete agreement with the experimental findings. Single trajectory simulations were sampled to report the time gap between the formation of C-C and C-O bonds. The extent and asynchronicity of bond formation was predicted from the computed Wiberg bond indices. SOPT analysis has been performed to highlight the appreciable delocalizations in the located transition states.

Keywords : 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition, transition state, interaction energy, trajectory.

Introduction

Stereochemically defined isoxazolidines¹ are synthesized by nitron cycloadditions. Different procedures²⁻⁵ have been attempted by various research groups to synthesize isoxazolidines having antibacterial activities. These include one of our approaches³ for the synthesis of stereochemically assigned isoxazolidines by the reaction of *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitron, **1** (Fig. 1) with methyl vinyl ketone, **2** (Fig. 1). The reaction proceeds via *exo*

pathway. The present report is DFT analysis for the favourable stereo and regiochemical pathway along the reaction channel.

The regio and stereoselectivities originated in nitron cycloadditions are analyzed by different theoretical approaches, mainly the computational studies⁶ involving conceptual DFT interpretations. However a generalized theoretical model has not yet been reported in literature to analyze these types of reactions. Several reactivity in-

Fig. 1. Cycloaddition reaction of nitron **1** to dipolarophile **2**.

dices have been introduced⁷⁻⁹ to explain the regioselectivities of such reactions. In the present study, the preferred regio and stereochemical attack has been predicted and were in complete agreement with the reported experimental findings³. Electronic chemical potentials¹⁰, global hardness¹⁰, electrophilicity indices¹⁰, interaction energies¹¹ and the activation parameters were computed at DFT/B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory. For the prediction of preferred stereochemical pathway, SOPT (Second Order Perturbation Theory) analysis was carried out to identify the appreciable delocalizations involved in the located transition states.

Computational methods :

The electronic chemical potential μ ¹² and chemical hardness η ¹³ were evaluated from the DFT calculated ionization potentials (I)¹⁴ and electron affinities (A)¹⁴. The global electrophilicity index ω ^{10,15} can be simply expressed by;

$$\omega = \mu^2 / 2\eta \quad (1)$$

The global softness S is given by;

$$S = 1/2\eta^{16} \quad (2)$$

Domingo *et al.*¹⁷ have recently proposed the Parr functions which are given as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} P^-(r) &= \rho^{rc}(r) \text{ for electrophilic attack} \\ P^+(r) &= \rho^{ra}(r) \text{ for nucleophilic attack} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\rho^{rc}(r)$ is the atomic spin density (ASD) of the radical cation and $\rho^{ra}(r)$ is the ASD of the radical anion. Domingo *et al.*^{18,19} have recently introduced an empirical (relative) nucleophilicity index, N based on the HOMO energies obtained within the Kohn-Sham scheme and defined as

$$N = E_{\text{HOMO(Nu)}} - E_{\text{LUMO(TCE)}} \quad (4)$$

where TCE is tetracyanoethylene.

The local electrophilicity index ω_k and the local nucleophilicity index N_k can be expressed in terms of electrophilic and nucleophilic Parr functions as follows :

$$\omega_k = \omega P^+(r) \quad N_k = NP^-(r) \quad (5)$$

when a stable molecule A (formed by bonding of K atoms, N_A being the total no. of electrons in A) and a stable molecule B (formed by bonding of L atoms, N_B being the total no. of electrons in B) interact with each other, the interaction energy¹¹ from density functional theory (DFT)

is given by;

$$\Delta E_{\text{int}} = \Delta E_v + \Delta E_\mu \quad (6)$$

where ΔE_v and ΔE_μ are the energy changes at constant external potential and constant chemical potential respectively and are written as;

$$\Delta E_v \approx -1/2 \{ \{S_A S_B [\mu_A - \mu_B]^2\} / \{S_A + S_B\} \} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta E_\mu \approx -1/2 \{ \lambda / \{S_A + S_B\} \} \quad (8)$$

Fukui functions¹⁰ for nucleophilic [f_k^+] and electrophilic [f_k^-] attack of an atom in a molecule was computed in terms of the respective electron populations of the cationic, neutral and anionic systems. When the local viewpoint of one reactant is considered, ΔE_v and ΔE_μ in terms of condensed Fukui function f_k become;

$$\Delta E_v \approx -1/2 \{ \{S_A S_B f_k [\mu_A - \mu_B]^2\} / \{S_A f_k + S_B\} \} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta E_\mu \approx -1/2 \{ \lambda / \{f_k S_A + S_B\} \} \quad (10)$$

The interaction energy $(\Delta E_{\text{int}})_A^k$ can be rewritten in shorthand notation as;

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta E_{\text{int}})_A^k &\approx \Delta E_v + \lambda \Delta E'_\mu \text{ with} \\ \Delta E'_\mu &= \Delta E_\mu (\lambda = 1) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The parameter λ has been related to the deviation of total softness of interacting system AB from the sum of the softnesses of individual systems A and B. It has been defined somewhat arbitrarily in the literature²⁰⁻²². Gazquez pointed out that the factor λ is proportional to an effective no. of valence electrons taking part in the reaction. In the present study, following the work of Mendez *et al.*¹¹, it has been initially assumed here that λ is close to 1 and ΔE_μ is much more important than ΔE_v . Pal and Chandrakumar^{23,24} related the parameter λ as the change in electron densities at the interacting site before and after the interaction process and calculated the global and local interaction energies as given by eqs. (12) and (13).

$$\Delta E_{\text{int}} \approx \frac{-(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2}{2} \left(\frac{S_A S_B}{S_A + S_B} \right)_v - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\lambda}{S_A + S_B} \right)_\mu \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta E_{\text{int}}) &\approx \frac{-(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2}{2} \left(\frac{S_A f_{Ax} S_B}{S_A f_{Ax} + S_B} \right)_v \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\lambda}{S_A f_{Ax} + S_B} \right)_\mu \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

This change will give the effective number of valence electrons that have participated in the interaction process. An expression for the term λ can be written as the difference of electron densities of the system *A* before and after the interaction^{23,24}

$$\lambda_A = \sum_{i=1}^P \rho_{Ai}^{eq} - \sum_{i=1}^P \rho_{Ai}^0 \quad (14)$$

Alternately, the term λ can be defined as the difference of electron densities for system *B*.

$$\lambda_B = \sum_{j=1}^q \rho_{Bj}^{eq} - \sum_{j=1}^q \rho_{Bj}^0 \quad (15)$$

where the first term of the right-hand side of the eqs. (14) and (15) refer to the sum of the electron densities of each atom in *A* and *B* in the molecule *AB* at equilibrium, respectively, and the second terms in eqs. (14) and (15) refer to electron densities of each atom in the isolated systems *A* and *B*, respectively. The indices *p* and *q* are the number of atoms of the systems *A* and *B*, respectively. With this approach, λ appears to be much less than 1 and ΔE_μ and ΔE_ν may be quite comparable.

The geometries have been optimized by Density Functional Theory with Becke's²⁵ three-parameter hybrid exchange functional in combination with the gradient-corrected correlation functional of Lee, Yang and Parr²⁶ (B3LYP) using 6-311+G(d,p) basis set. The transition states have been localized at DFT/B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory. The stationary points were characterized through vibrational frequency analysis done at 298.15 K at the DFT/B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) level. All the stationary points are definitely identified for minima (number of imaginary frequencies = 0) or transition states (number of imaginary frequencies = 1). In accordance to the previous studies²⁷, intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC)²⁸ calculations were performed to verify that the energy curve connecting the optimized reactants and the products passes through the correct and the lowest TS which must be a

first-order saddle point. The electron affinity and ionization potential have been obtained at similar level using UB3LYP theory for the anion and cation. The geometries of the neutral species are used to calculate the electronic structure of the charged species in order to fulfill the demand for constant external potential. The electronic populations have been computed from natural population analysis²⁹. Gaussian jobs with the sampled initial conditions were automatically generated to propagate the trajectories (ADMP³⁰ keyword). The trajectories were run at 298 K using the default step size. All calculations were carried out using Gaussian 2003³¹ set of programs along with the graphical interface Gauss View 2003.

Results and discussion

Analysis based on electronic chemical potentials, global hardness, electrophilicities and local properties of the reactants :

The global properties of the reactants are tabulated in Table 1. Nitron **1** has higher electronic chemical potential (μ) than that of **2**. Therefore, charge transfer from nitron **1** to dipolarophile **2** is predicted for the cycloaddition. The calculated global electrophilicities ω of **1** and **2** are 0.855 eV and 1.194 eV which indicates that nitron **1** is less electrophilic than **2**. At the same time, nucleophilicity index N^{7-9} value predicts nitron **1** to be the better nucleophile than **2**. This also supports the predicted normal electron demand character.

Local properties are listed in Table 2. The local electrophilicity index ω_k and local nucleophilicity index N_k of the reactants can be employed to predict the regioselectivity of the reaction. ω_k and N_k values of the reaction centres indicate the most electrophilic and most nucleophilic centres in the reactants.

In case of nitron **1**, ω_k of C3 is greater than O1 hence C3 is more prone to nucleophilic attack but O1 is more prone to electrophilic attack. For **2**, C_β is more prone to nucleophilic attack and C_α is more prone to electrophilic attack. For the reaction system **1/2**, favoured

Table 1. DFT/B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) calculated global properties of the reactants

	Total energy (au)	HOMO energy (eV)	LUMO energy (eV)	μ (au)	η (au)	<i>S</i> (au)	ω (eV)	<i>N</i> (eV)
1	-534.960433	-5.279	-1.442	-0.130	0.269	1.859	0.855	4.190
2	-231.307327	-7.156	-2.014	-0.175	0.349	1.433	1.194	2.313

Table 2. DFT/B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculated local properties of the reactants **1-2**

	<i>k</i>	$P^-(r)$	$P^+(r)$	ω_k	N_k
1	O1	0.527	0.060	0.051	2.208
	C3	0.084	0.500	0.428	0.352
2	C_α	0.128	0.011	0.013	0.296
	C_β	-0.039	0.552	0.659	-0.090

interaction occurs when C_α of **2** takes up a nucleophilic attack on C3 of **1** and C_β of **2** takes up an electrophilic attack on O1 of **1**. These interaction leads to the formation of *meta* isomer, and is not in agreement with the experimental findings. Therefore, interaction energies for this reaction were calculated and analyzed to predict the regiochemistry of the investigated reactions.

Analysis based on interaction energy calculation :

We have recently employed interaction energy calculations to predict the regioselectivities of the cycloaddition reactions of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl nitron to methyl crotonate³², chalcones³³, styrene³⁴, ethyl cinnamate³⁴ and β -nitro styrene³⁴. For the present study, λ has been analyzed by two different approaches. The exact value of λ is difficult to determine with a simple model since the positive factor λ may be different for different 1,3-dipole-dipolarophile couples. The value of λ was obtained by factors yielding at least an order of magnitude 1 in the report of Gazquez²⁰⁻²². It has been coined as approach *A* for the present report. With approach *A* consideration, the more important term is $\Delta E'_\mu$ as can be anticipated from the small difference in chemical potentials. Pal and Chandrakumar^{23,24} related the parameter λ as the change in the electron densities at the interacting site before and after the interaction process. This approach is termed as *B*. λ values calculated from eq. (14) by natural population analysis for **1/2** system is 0.0056. Keeping in mind the electronic chemical potentials and electrophilicities of the reactants, the nucleophilic attack by dipole **1** to the dipolarophile **2** can be considered for **1/2**. The calculated interaction energy values from approach *A* and *B* have been listed in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively.

The favourable interaction is predicted between C3 (electrophilic attack) and C_α (nucleophilic attack) by approach *A*. This interaction leads to the formation of *meta* regioisomer. However, the prediction is different by approach *B*. The interaction between C3 (electrophilic at-

tack) and C_β (nucleophilic attack) is preferred in accordance with approach *B*. This prediction is in complete agreement with experimental findings. Therefore λ value calculation by approach *B* provides correct prediction for the regiochemistry of the investigated reaction.

Nature of transition states :

The optimized geometries of reactants products and transition states were specified by the naming system employed in our previous DFT studies^{32,33}. The *ortho* reaction channel is prefixed by 'o' and the *meta* channel by 'm'. The *endo* and *exo* modes have been coined as *n* and *x* respectively. Therefore, *endo/ortho* and *exo/ortho* products are pno and pxo respectively and the respective transition states are tno and txo. For the *meta* regioisomers, unrealistic results and transition states structures were found for the reaction system. The inability for the prediction of regioselectivity was also found for the related reactions³⁵. This was also been pointed out in our previous communications^{27,33}. It was further concluded by Domingo *et al.*^{36,37} the predictions of regioselectivity are highly dependent on the computational levels. Interaction energy calculations predict the regioselectivity more accurately. The optimized geometries of products and transition states along the *ortho* channel are shown in Fig. 2.

The bond lengths, bond orders, charge transfer and the other parameters are listed in Table 5. For tno and txo, the length of forming C3-C4 bond (2.059 Å and 2.051 Å) is shorter than forming C5-O1 bond (2.291 Å and 2.311 Å). The atom-atom overlap weighted NAO bond order values indicate asynchronicity for the concerted cycloaddition reactions. Jasiński *et al.*³⁸ also reported that B3LYP/6-31G(d) calculations perfectly illustrate the structure of transition states in cycloadditions between diarylnitrones and 1-EWG-2-arylethenes. Jasiński *et al.*³⁹ reported the application of bond development indices I_{C3-C4} and I_{C5-O1} calculated by the relations

$$I_{C3-C4} = 1 - [\{r^{TS}_{C3-C4} - r^P_{C3-C4}\}/r^P_{C3-C4}]$$

$$I_{C5-O1} = 1 - [\{r^{TS}_{C5-O1} - r^P_{C5-O1}\}/r^P_{C5-O1}]$$

to explain the bond formation in cycloaddition reactions of 2-nitropropene-1 to *Z*-*C,N*-diaryl nitrones. The asymmetry indices Δa as the absolute values of the differences between I_{C3-C4} and I_{C5-O1} was further defined by them. In the present study, for tno and txo, the bond develop-

Fig. 2. DFT/B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p) optimized product and transition state.

ment indices predict the more rapid formation of C3-C4 bond compared to C5-O1 bond. Δa for tno is greater than that of txo.

Hence the *endo* and *exo* pathways for the reaction

system are asynchronous. Leroy *et al.*⁴⁰, has introduced the term $t = -\sum q_A$ where q_A is the net charge and the sum is taken over all the atoms of the dipolarophile. The calculated charge transferred for 1/2 reaction channels reveal an almost neutral reaction and an electron flow from the nitron to the dipolarophile, the electronic chemical potential values and global electrophilicity indices of **1** and **2** (Table 1) also state this fact.

Analysis based on activation parameters and rate constant values :

In Table 6, the activation parameters have been listed. The *exo* channel is preferred over *endo* channel by 7.598 kJ mol⁻¹. ΔG^\ddagger of *exo* isomer is stabilized by 7.494 kJ mol⁻¹ compared to the *endo* product. The *exo* product was obtained as the sole product experimentally³.

Analysis based on SOPT :

Inter reactant delocalizations⁴¹ are likely to contribute in the formation of the preferred isomer through the favoured transition state. For the present study, we obtained the evidences of such delocalizations from second order perturbation theory analysis. Let us get a brief report for the appreciable delocalizations in the transition states along the different reaction channels.

For the reaction system 1/2, SOPT analysis suggests that the delocalization from dipolarophile **2** to nitron **1** is stabilized by 124.70 kJ mol⁻¹ for transition state txo

Table 5. Bond lengths ($r/\text{\AA}$), Wiberg bond indices (a), atom-atom overlap weighted NAO bond orders (b), charge transfer (CT), bond development indices (I), and asymmetry indices (Δa) of the located transition states

p/ts	O1-N1	N2-C3	C3-C4	C4-C5	C5-O1	a_{C3-C4}	a_{C5-O1}	b_{C3-C4}	b_{C5-O1}	I_{C3-C4}	I_{C5-O1}	Δa	CT
1	1.297	1.314	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	-	-	1.334	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
pno	1.443	1.481	1.541	1.534	1.461	0.985	0.885	0.861	0.711	-	-	-	-
tno	1.293	1.362	2.059	1.390	2.291	0.470	0.247	0.403	0.140	0.664	0.432	0.232	0.063
pxo	1.431	1.490	1.541	1.535	1.467	0.985	0.875	0.861	0.689	-	-	-	-
txo	1.297	1.363	2.051	1.389	2.311	0.466	0.251	0.402	0.133	0.669	0.575	0.094	0.046

Table 6. DFT/B3LYP/6-311G+(d,p) calculated energies for the reaction channels

Configuration of the approaching reactants	Optimized product energies (au)	ts	Optimized energies (au)	Transition states		
				Activation parameters (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
				ΔE^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	ΔH^\ddagger
1 + 2 (<i>endo/ortho</i>)	-766.293809	tno	-766.247198	53.980	115.890	57.417
1 + 2 (<i>exo/ortho</i>)	-766.295832	txo	-766.250092	46.382	108.396	50.375

compared to tno. Moreover, the delocalization from nitrene **1** to dipolarophile **2** in tno is stabilized by 113.273 kJ mol⁻¹ for transition state tno compared to tno. This underlines the predominant formation of the *exo* product by the favoured transition state. Both the transition states tno and tno showed appreciable π - π^* delocalization between the bonding orbital of C=C bond of the dipolarophile **2** and the antibonding orbital of the C-N bond of nitrene **1**. π - π^* delocalization was also noted with remarkable energy between the bonding orbital of C-N bond of nitrene **1** and the antibonding orbital of the C=C bond of the dipolarophile **2**. For both the transition states, appreciable n - π^* delocalization was noted between lone pair orbital of O1 of **1** and the antibonding orbital of the C=C bond of the dipolarophile **2**.

Analysis based on trajectory analysis :

Huisgen⁴² and Firestone⁴³ concluded different mechanisms for the bond formation process in dipolar cycloadditions. The concerted approach established by Huisgen⁴² rationalized the reactivities, selectivities, lack of trappable intermediates and substituent effects for such reactions. On the contrary, Firestone reported a stepwise mechanism via diradical intermediate for dipolar cycloadditions. This mechanism proposed the initial formation of one σ bond with the generation of an unstable diradical intermediate which is short lived and cyclizes before C-C bond rotation. Consequently, the stereochemistry is retained in the process. A dynamics⁴⁴ calculation is therefore necessary to establish the differences between the concerted pathway and Firestone's mechanism of diradical intermediates. We have recently⁴⁵ applied these calculations to rationalize the cycloadditions of 1-cinnamoyl-1-piperidine. In the present study, single trajectory calculations were carried out for the *endo* and *exo* reaction modes of **1/2** reaction system. The time gaps (in femtosecond) were calculated between the formations of two bonds in single trajectories. Here, two bonding definitions have been employed. The first bond length value used is 1.8 Å in single trajectory simulations. This value is longer than the product bond distance. The second value used is 2.0 Å. This is close to the forming bond distances of the transition states. For **1/2** reaction channel, the calculated time gaps are 9.2 fs (for 1.8 Å) and 12.3 fs (2.0 Å) for the *endo/ortho* mode. The corresponding *exo/ortho* pathway indicates time gaps of 19.3 fs and 22.2 fs for 1.8 Å

and 2.0 Å respectively. The trajectory analysis predicts more rapid formation of C3-C4 bond compared to C5-O1 bond. This is in complete agreement with the bond development indices. The time gap data for both the reaction channels indicate a concerted mechanism where both C-O and C-C bonds are formed within a vibrational period. This suggests that no diradical is formed on the surface which has a greater lifetime than that required by those atoms to undergo a vibration needed for bond formation. Therefore, the cyclo-diradical mechanism is not supported by the above data. This confirms the concerted nature of the involved reaction mechanism of the investigated cycloaddition reactions.

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